

XI CONGRESO IBÉRICO SOBRE RECURSOS GENÉTICOS ANIMALES

Congreso Internacional

Sociedad Española para los Recursos Genéticos Animales (**SERGA**)

Sociedade Portuguesa de Recursos Genéticos Animais (**SPREGA**)

SERGA

Libro de resúmenes

Instituto Murciano de Investigación y Desarrollo Agrario y Alimentario (IMIDA)

Fundación Séneca de la Región de Murcia

f SéNeCa⁽⁺⁾

Agencia de Ciencia y Tecnología
Región de Murcia

Murcia, 27 y 28 de septiembre de 2018

Resúmenes XI Congreso Ibérico para los Recursos
Genéticos Animales

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INFLUENCE OF TRADITIONAL AND INNOVATIVE FOODS ON THE CARCASS QUALITY OF THE BÍSARA SWINE BREED

João Santos SILVA (1), Joaquim Lima CERQUEIRA (2,3), Preciosa PIRES (4), Benedicte LEBRET (5), Marjeta CANDEK-POTOKAR (6), José Pedro ARAÚJO (2,7)

(1) Ministério da Agricultura, Florestas e Desenvolvimento Rural, Guimarães, Portugal (ippsss@gmail.com; joao.silva@drapnorte.pt;

(2) Escola Superior Agrária, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, 4990-706, Ponte de Lima, Portugal

(3) CECAV, Animal and Veterinary Research Centre, UTAD, Vila Real, Portugal

(4) Escola Superior de Tecnologia e Gestão, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Portugal

(5) INRA, UMR PEGASE 35590 Saint-Gilles, France

(6) Kis-Agricultural Institute of Slovenia, Ljubljana, Slovenia.

(7) Centro de Investigação de Montanha, ESA-IPVC, Portugal

In Portugal, the traditional livestock system of the swine breed Bísara valorises a diversity of traditional foods to generate a multiplicity of products under Certified Quality System (DPO, PGI or STG). The overall objective of this work was to evaluate the effect of traditional and innovative feed resources on carcass traits of the Bísara breed.

A total of 30 pigs, with 3 months age, were distributed in number and gender in three batches (5 castrated males and 5 females), placed in a semi-extensive system with a hoop barn with outdoor free access (200 m²/pig). The animals were controlled in two phases: Phase 1 (20 to 80 kg LW) with a equivalent feeding diet for all animals; Phase 2 (finishing, 80 to 120 kg LW) diets differed according to the lots: D1- germinated seeds, concentrate and corn meal; D2- potatoes, concentrate and corn meal; D3- concentrate and corn meal. Data were subjected to a least-squares analysis of variances (ANOVA) using the general linear models (GLM), including diet and sex effects and its interactions, and slaughter weight was introduced as covariate in the model.

The diet influenced ($P < 0.01$) the weight gain during the finishing period (D1: 0,385 kg/d, D2: 0,451 kg/d, D3: 0,530 kg/d).

The animals were slaughtered at the same weight ($120,5 \pm 13,1$ kg LW) and no effect ($P > 0.05$) of the diet was observed on the slaughter weight. Sexual effect was observed on slaughter weight ($m = 128,1$ vs $f = 113,9$ kg LW).

Diets influenced ($P < 0,05$) the following traits: Ham length (D1=40,3; D2=40,6; D3=38,6 cm); Cinnamon perimeter (D1=15,8; D2=15,4; D3=16,4 cm); back fat thickness at point DFT3 (D1=3,9; D2=4,4; D3=4,2 cm); lean meat percentage (D1=40,7; D2=35,5, D3=35,0 %). The sex influenced ($P < 0,05$) body and carcass weight at slaughter and lean meat percentage: the males were heavier at slaughter ($128,1$ vs $113,8$ Kg LW), and fatter than females ($34,4$ vs $39,8$ % of lean).

Keywords: autochthones breeds, rearing systems, meat quality.

Acknowledgments: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 634476 (Project acronym: TREASURE). The content of this paper reflects only the

author's view and the European Union Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.